

Serendipity, AI and climate science: The role of non-linear thinking

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This first piece of 2024 introduces some ideas concerning the role of non-linear thinking in today's fight against the climate crisis. More exactly, it is about the potential power of serendipity, artificial intelligence and the information deluge (that is causing headaches, too) when it comes to humankind's efforts to find solutions for the sake of surviving the paramount crisis.

Some of the ideas are new, such as [1-2].

Some have been around for some time [3-4].

Illustration: Serendipity drawn by Bing Chat AI.

Nonetheless, these all serve a single purpose of empowering our fight against the climate crisis based on potential innovations that leverage the strengths we can gain from nature, the same way living things have been doing so well for billions of years. To this end, serendipity and non-linear thinking serve as keywords [5].

References

- [1] Vuong QH, La VP, Nguyen MH. (2024). Serendipity and inherent non-linear thinking can help address the climate and environmental conundrums. <https://philarchive.org/rec/VUOSAI>
- [2] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2023). How an Age-old Photo of Little Chicks Can Awaken Our Conscience for Biodiversity Conservation and Nature Protection. <https://philarchive.org/rec/VUOHAA>
- [3] Vuong QH, Ho MT. (2024). Escape climate apathy by harnessing the power of generative AI. *AI & Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-023-01830-x>
- [4] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). Kingfisher: contemplating the connection between nature and humans through science, art, literature, and lived experiences. *Pacific Conservation Biology*. <https://doi.org/10.1071/PC23044>
- [5] Vuong QH. (Ed.)(2022). *A New Theory of Serendipity: Nature, Emergence and Mechanism*. De Gruyter. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0C5C4LPF1>

